

THE CONCEPT OF NATIONAL-MORAL AND ESTHETIC VALUES IN THE POLITICAL HERITAGE OF THE GREAT LEADER OF THE AZERBAIJAN PEOPLE, HEYDAR ALIYEV

Khatire Guliyeva

Doctor of Sciences in Philosophy. Associate Professor. Head of the Department of "Philosophy of Identity, Multiculturalism and Azerbaijanism" at the Institute of Philosophy and Sociology of the Azerbaijan National Academy of Sciences

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4889-6569>

Summary

It is known that events related to national-spiritual values or ethno-identity, as a whole, philosophical-ethical existence, are of great importance in the life of every nation. It is no coincidence that national-spiritual values, which affect human consciousness from the womb to death, have historically transformative power in terms of philosophical content and essence.

Of course, no matter how natural the development of this dialectically powerful actor in the process of changing the location of civilizations is, its decline and fall have also been confirmed in practice.

The most important factor for the development and survival of this factor is the State, the head of state - the Leader. In other words, the state of national-spiritual values, which form the basis of the history of nations, depends on the state and the head of state.

This article analyzes the attitude of Heydar Aliyev, one of the geniuses of the 20th century, the eternal national leader of the Azerbaijani people - the Great Leader, who protected and strengthened the national and spiritual values of his people during the period of independence of our country and even during the regime and deprivation system of the Soviet empire, to this concept of national self-awareness, which is of historical importance, during his leadership activity covering many decades.

In our opinion, the analysis, facts and assessments of the attitude of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev to events covering everything from language, religion, holidays to national genocides, national tragedies, national customs and traditions and their philosophical and moral thought will open a serious page in world science, world scientific thought and political and philosophical history on such important issues as Nation - State, National Leader - Nation.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Heydar Alirza oglu Aliyev, national leader

Introduction

The system of national-spiritual-aesthetic values represents an identity phenomenon characterized by psychological roots developed and possessed by a certain people over millennia and transmitted in its conceptual content to future generations, both geopolitical and ethnonational, as well as to the family and to the individual citizen as a whole.

These national-spiritual-aesthetic values are also an area of such a comprehensive, broad, specific and synthetic nature that by studying them, one can determine the national idea, national worldview and national self-awareness, including broad customs and traditions, as well as a philosophy of life that encompasses ethical and aesthetic national existence.

The system of national-spiritual and literary-aesthetic values, that is, the phenomenon of ethnic-national self-awareness, formed over the centuries, in a broad sense represents the common morality and culture of a people - religious worldview, ethical and aesthetic views, oral

literature based on mythological sources, folk creativity, written literature and professional art forms, etc. It contains the essence expressed in identity through self-improvement.

Undoubtedly, the main foundations of national-spiritual and literary-aesthetic values - space, language, religion, national customs and traditions, even the status of heads of families belonging to the same ethnic group - no matter how much they are subject to renewal, their uniqueness is inseparable from their roots; they have a national self-awareness and spiritual heritage.

In this regard, spiritual values express a very strong and subtle national-psychological, ethical and socio-cultural content, through which the common national psychology, philosophical and moral ideas, aesthetic consciousness, religious views and unified culture of the people are revealed.

Main part

1.1 The Strategy of National-Moral and Aesthetic Values in Heydar Aliyev's Political Governance System

One of the well-known scientists of Azerbaijan, Academician Afrand Dashdemirov, like all researchers studying the sources of the synthesis of the national idea related to the ethnic layers of national culture, puts forward the following specific idea that is consistent with our opinion: "The ethnic roots and ethnic components of Azerbaijani culture have existed in the national self-awareness of our people for several millennia, preserving its spiritual and historical identity and preserving its cultural sovereignty. They play a unique role"¹.

National-spiritual and literary-aesthetic values - the general system of the national self-awareness system or national mentality, ideas and ideology - is a phenomenon created by history, which wrote history in its time and was later remembered with its own systems, and which has a great renaissance power as the supreme political act of the Great Leader of the Azerbaijani people, Heydar Aliyev. This phenomenon was the concept of national state building of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev and is the main principle of his national state policy. More precisely, the Strategy of National-Moral and Literary-Aesthetic Values, which is of great philosophical and political importance in the state policy of the Great Leader, is characterized as the main principle of political governance of the State of Azerbaijan.

Researcher Afshan Shafiyeva, in her article "Assessment of Modern Azerbaijani History in the Legacy of Heydar Aliyev", assesses the importance of national-spiritual values in the political leadership of the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev as follows: "The main factor that makes the problem relevant is that in many cases the ideals of complete spirituality and multilateral integration contradict the heritage formed over the centuries - they are directed against national-spiritual values. Heydar Aliyev, thanks to his political foresight and patriotism, immediately neutralized this threat, constantly monitored it and took preventive measures. The love of this great personality for his homeland, national heritage and traditions served to preserve the genetic memory of our people.

Heydar Aliyev was deeply attached to the culture, history and traditions of Azerbaijan, which have stood the test of millennia, and spared no effort to return them to the people in their original form.

He was extremely attached to his culture, history and traditions and did everything in his power to return them to the people in their original form. A deep understanding of human history, including the history of Azerbaijan, its ancient roots and the values on which it was founded"². Based on Azerbaijani statehood and Azerbaijani identity, the National Leader Heydar Aliyev has always kept this important issue "in the spotlight". The special attention paid by the

¹ Daşdemirov A. Millət və cəmiyyət tarixinə sərt dönəmində. Bakı, Elm. 2008.p.121. 344 pag..

² Shafiyeva Afshan. Assessment of Modern Azerbaijani History in the Legacy of Heydar Aliyev. Journal of Academic History and Ideas. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/atdd/article/1350542>.

National Leader Heydar Aliyev to national values in state policy, the importance he attached to maintaining balance with national values, as well as his practical steps in this area - the decrees he issued on our national values, the analysis of the work done to protect and promote these values, give grounds to say that national values were not a priority in state policy at that time. No aspect of our values was overlooked, and necessary measures were taken for their development, protection and transmission to future generations. Just as our spiritual values were in the spotlight, our material assets, historical monuments and examples of material culture, which have already become our national assets, were restored and complex measures were taken to expand the work done in this area¹.

It should be noted here that Heydar Aliyev, who thought about the ideology of the national identity policy of the independent republic, the management strategy and the national-spiritual, literary and aesthetic values of our people, always kept the national language in mind as a basic concept during both periods of his political power, systematically formed and developed it.

Thus, Heydar Aliyev, on his personal initiative and, most importantly, in accordance with the dictates of his national spirit, achieved the inclusion of Article 73, which was not yet applied in other Soviet republics, into the Constitution of the Azerbaijan SSR adopted in 1978. With true dedication and heroism, he unconditionally ensured the interests of the Great Leader, while at the same time creating an independent Azerbaijani national state in our native language. National and civil relations proved to be strong.

1.2 National Language Strategy in the Political Administration of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev

Heydar Aliyev was deeply attached to the culture, history and traditions of Azerbaijan, which have stood the test of millennia, and spared no effort to return them to the people in their original form

"Having a deep knowledge of the history of mankind, including the history of Azerbaijan, its ancient roots and the values on which the formation of Azerbaijani statehood and Azerbaijani identity was based, the National Leader Heydar Aliyev always kept this important issue in the spotlight." The fact that National Leader Heydar Aliyev paid special attention to national values in state policy and the importance he attached to maintaining balance in these relations, as well as the practical steps taken in this area - issuing decrees on our national values, analyzing the work done to protect and promote these values, gives reason to say that no area of our national values was overlooked in the state policy of that period. Necessary measures were taken for their development, protection and transmission to future generations. Just as our spiritual values are in the spotlight, material assets, historical monuments and examples of material culture that have already become national treasures are also being restored, and complex measures are being taken to expand work in this area.

It should be especially noted here that the independent Heydar Aliyev, who thought about the ideology of the republic's national identity policy, management strategy, and the national-spiritual and literary-aesthetic values of our people, always kept the national language in mind as a fundamental concept during both periods of his political power, systematically formed and developed it.

1.3 National Language Strategy in the Political Administration of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev

When analyzing and evaluating the National Language Strategy in the political administration of the national leader Heydar Aliyev, it is necessary to note, first of all, his personal initiative and the dictates of the national spirit. With true dedication and heroism, the

¹Shafiyeva Afshan. Assessment of Modern Azerbaijani History in the Legacy of Heydar Aliyev. Journal of Academic History and Ideas. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/atdd/article/1350542>.

great leader Heydar Aliyev achieved the inclusion of Article 73 in the Constitution of the Azerbaijan SSR adopted in 1978. This article had not yet been applied in other Soviet republics. This was the expression of the State-Nation ideology of the Great Leader in the construction of an independent national state of Azerbaijan, as well as the attitude of a national citizen to the native language of the nation, of which he was the political leader.

Thus, "On April 2, 1978, at the 7th session of the Supreme Soviet of the Azerbaijan SSR of the 9th convocation, at the proposal of Heydar Aliyev, who made a report on the draft Constitution (Fundamental Law) of the Azerbaijan Soviet Socialist Republic and the results of its nationwide discussion, it was proposed to revise Article 73 as follows¹.

Based on the documents of various representatives of the people, the memories of intellectuals, writers and scientists, the objective conclusion is that Heydar Aliyev's achievement of including this article in the 1978 Constitution can be considered a complex and historical event in terms of the realization of the constitutional demands of the generation of global educators. On the one hand, taking into account the peculiarities of the political system of that period, as well as the danger of the regime, the lack of such experience, and on the other hand, taking into account its non-application in very large and imperially close republics, this great service that Heydar Aliyev truly rendered to his people and homeland is an example of true revolutionary heroism. After endless tense negotiations in Moscow, the great historical figure Heydar Aliyev proposed the Constitution. Azerbaijan, in its current form, adopted was made, laid the foundation for the once close independent statehood and gave the Azerbaijani language the status of a state language.

This constitutional article began important measures for the development and protection of our native language and at the same time first and seriously emphasized independence from the ideology of the entire Soviet Union.

After the Republic of Azerbaijan gained independence for the second time, Heydar Aliyev, who began to fulfill his mission as a nation-builder from the chair of the supreme political leader in accordance with the general will and demand of the people, decided to strengthen the national spirit and develop our native language by creating our national constitution, which forms the foundation of any civil and legal society. By signing it, the Azerbaijani language received a new and full state status.

This decision determined the legal and moral character of the state, its respectful approach to its national and spiritual heritage.

The Great Leader Heydar Aliyev, at the First Congress of World Azerbaijanis, adopted the Resolution on the National Language, and at the same time, particularly appreciated the phenomenon of the national language in the relations between the state and the nation, the nation and the state.

In this regard, the ideas of the Great Leader, as expressed in the following quote, are of interest in the programmatic nature of his rich political heritage: "The broad Decision we have adopted on the development of the Azerbaijani language has precisely this purpose. We have adopted a decision on the transition of Azerbaijan to the Latin alphabet. Now everyone in Azerbaijan, all state bodies use only the Latin alphabet. This is a very important factor that shows our nationality and Azerbaijaniness. We will continue our efforts to develop the Azerbaijani language in the future"².

Also, Heydar Aliyev's profound ideas about language, which are like aphorisms today, fully express his Azerbaijani ideas and goals: "It is the language of each people that keeps alive and develops its nationality and spiritual values"³; "People who do not know their native

¹ Azərbaycan Sovet Sosialist Respublikasının dövlət dili Azərbaycan dilidir (Konstitutsiya https://files.preslib.az/projects/remz/pdf/atr_dil.pdf).

² Heydər Əliyevin Dünya Azərbaycanlılarının 1-ci qurultayında nitqi https://az.wikisource.org/wiki/D%C3%BCn-ya_Az%C9%99rbaycanl%C4%B1lar_nitqi.

³ Heydər Əliyev. Müdrik fikirlər. <http://www.heydar-aliyev-foundation.org/az/content/index/85/>

language are crippled people"¹; "We are now proud of our own language, the Azerbaijani language, as an independent state, as a free people"². ...“Every nation is born with its own language. However, the survival, development and raising of the nation to the level of world culture is possible as a result of the activities of the leading people of the nation, scientists and intellectuals”³.

Heydar Aliyev, in front of the broad masses of the people, as well as at state events, and even in the memory of many, gave a recommendation to everyone to learn their native language, making impressive words and profound speeches in the Azerbaijani language. At the same time, the great leader systematically implemented his goal in this direction in the country's constitution, as well as in the education law.

Another important area in the "Strategy of National and Spiritual Values" of the Great Leader of the Azerbaijani people Heydar Aliyev, who highly values the national and spiritual heritage created by our ancient ancestors and preserved and perpetuated by our people from time to time, as a state management policy, is the phenomenon of religious belief, Islamic ethics and culture.

We will analyze this topic in the following section.

1.3 The attitude of the National Leader Heydar Aliyev to the holy religion of Islam in the context of state policy

Religion is as important a factor and a necessary issue in the history and fate of peoples and nations as language. Democratic-minded people are attached to this factor, which is the national feeling of peoples, and true national leaders always keep it in the spotlight. For this, of course, the ethnopsychological identity qualities of the individual, especially the "intellectual self", are the basis.

The fact that the National Leader Heydar Aliyev, who had high intelligence and high moral qualities, was born in a family loyal to our holy religion and was raised in the spirit of Islamic values, undoubtedly influenced his future life and fate. The Great Leader had deep respect for the religion to which he belonged until the end of his life and seriously protected, defended and developed it during his political power.

Another characteristic historical fact. President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Heydar Aliyev, in his speech on March 20, 1999, at a meeting with pilgrims who were going on Hajj pilgrimage at the invitation of the King of Saudi Arabia and Custodian of the Two Holy Mosques Fahd ibn Abdulaziz, expressed his wise thoughts in the following sentences:

“I wish you all a good journey. I wish in advance that God will accept your Hajj pilgrimage and that you return safely to our homeland. I am very pleased to meet you again on this festive evening, on this dear, holy day. Because on such a day, every meeting is of special importance for a person. I meet you, that is, I meet people who are going on Hajj pilgrimage for the sake of God.

Convey my greetings from me to Mecca, Medina and the Kaaba and convey to them with your own feelings how devoted the Azerbaijani people are to all the high spiritual values of the Islamic religion. Have a nice trip! I congratulate you once again on your holiday. I wish you all good health and success in all your endeavors. God preserves”⁴.

It should be noted that after Heydar Aliyev's visit to the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia in 1994, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, personally led by King Fahd bin Abdulaziz Al Saud, organized

¹ There agae

² There agae

³ XXI Əsr: ümid və çağırışları adlı forum. <http://bakuforum.az/az/multikulturalizm-nailiyyetler-ve-problem-ler/?fid=2258>

⁴ Guliyeva Khatira. [Heydər Əliyev və Azərbaycan Respublikası - Səudiyyə Ərəbistanı Krallığı qarşılıqlı münasibətləri](https://science.gov.az/az/news/open/24246) <https://science.gov.az/az/news/open/24246>; Azərbaycan – Səudiyyə Ərəbistanı münasibətləri. <https://lib.aliyev-heritage.org/az/7892915.html> <https://lib.aliyev-heritage.org/az/8325749.html>

the Hajj pilgrimage of 250 people from Azerbaijan every year. This reality is fully reflected in the following quote from Heydar Aliyev:

"The desire of each of you to visit Mecca, Medina and the Kaaba in itself reflects your inner spirituality. Every person who wants to visit those holy places must embark on a high spiritual path, and I hope that you have realized this and have desired to visit Mecca, Medina and the Kaaba, and this desire is already coming true.

You are on your way, you are going. You and we - all of us - are grateful to the King of Saudi Arabia, the Custodian of the Two Holy Mosques, our friend and brother, for this care and attention shown to Azerbaijan.

This has already become a tradition. Every year, during the Hajj pilgrimage, Azerbaijan is shown such care, and now 250 people go on the Hajj pilgrimage as guests of the King of Saudi Arabia. The Hajj pilgrimage itself is a great blessing for a person. However, performing this pilgrimage under the patronage of the guardians of the two holy shrines gives it even more special significance"¹.

Indeed, as the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev emphasized, the national spiritual values of the Azerbaijani people have formed a synthesis with the philosophy of life instilled by the Islamic religion to which our people belong, and from time to time they have created and developed their own philosophical moral norms. In this process, the Great Leader of the Azerbaijani people, Heydar Aliyev, had a special role as the head of state. The Great Leader combined the philosophy of life of the Islamic religion in the unity of the State-Nation, the Nation-State, and the goal of solidarity. That is why his state governance policy is of extraordinary importance in the process of national self-awareness and self-affirmation of the Azerbaijani people.

The book titled "Heydar Aliyev" also expresses thoughts about the religious qualities of the Great Leader of the Azerbaijani People, Heydar Aliyev: "He was a prophetic personality who invited everyone only to good deeds. Heydar Aliyev lived like this both during the years when the Quran and the Bible were banned and later. He saw the results of his good deeds and pure intentions. He died knowing that he had fulfilled the sacred duty set before him by God".

While concluding our analysis in this section, we must note with scientific and objectiveness that the national idea phenomenon, which originated from the national-spiritual foundations of our people, has led to the growth of new generations of progressive people in the continuation of civilizations, the strengthening of the policy pursued by the state with the advanced ideas of enlightened thinkers, and their return to strengthen the national idea"².

2. Evaluation of the Model of Aesthetic National-Spiritual Heritage of Azerbaijan in Heydar Aliyev's Political System

Peoples and nations that build their lives on national-spiritual values naturally form and develop a national idea stemming from their traditions. Just as the historical ethno-identity criteria of this or that people, that is, the consciousness of national "self", lie at the root of the national idea, the interests of the homeland, state, people, and nation, connected to those foundations, lie on its upper layer. Without this, the viability of the national idea cannot be imagined. Another issue is that the national idea finds its full expression in artistic works, which are the product of the ethical norms, moral style, philosophical thinking, and creative aesthetic consciousness of the people formed over many centuries.

This spiritual heritage, firstly, cultivates a new person, personality and national spirit; secondly, it conditions the strengthening of national ideology with this innovation; thirdly, it not

¹ Azərbaycan – Səudiyyə Ərəbstanı münasibətləri. <https://lib.aliyev-heritage.org/az/7892915.html> <https://lib.aliyev-heritage.org/az/8325749.html>

² Heydər Əliyev və Azərbaycan ədəbiyyatı, Bakı, Elm-1998. səh. 36. 240 səh.

only determines the development of individual creative spheres, but also advances the ideas of the era with these means of influence.

After Heydar Aliyev came to political power for the second time and implemented it through universal suffrage during the Soviet era, he adopted important state decisions, decrees and orders with the aim of re-learning and re-evaluating everything from scratch, from tradition, in the field of national and spiritual values, which were purely Marxist-Leninist ideological at that time.

After Heydar Aliyev came to political power for the second time through universal suffrage, he adopted important state decisions, decrees and orders with the aim of learning and re-evaluating everything in the field of national and spiritual values from scratch, from tradition. This led to the restoration of national holidays and days of mourning, which were deliberately and biasedly evaluated and prevented from being celebrated with solemnity during the Soviet period, which were excluded from scientific research and analysis purely on the basis of Marxist-Leninist ideology, and a revival in the field of folk creative heritage.

Among the works carried out by Heydar Aliyev, who, first of all, preserved the spiritual heritage representing the national historical memory as a national leader and a true citizen, at the state level, the solemn celebration of Novruz Bayram, which is one of the main sources of the philosophical worldview of the Azerbaijani people, our aesthetic and ethical consciousness, is one of the clearest examples. Heydar Aliyev's signing of the official Decree on the celebration of Novruz Bayram as a national holiday, his joining this mass folk festival traditionally held every year in Baku's Youth Square, in front of the Gosha Gala Gate, and welcoming Novruz together with Baku workers on the first day of spring, remain as the most unforgettable memories in the memory of our people.

The Great Leader, who worked to ensure that every national tradition lives on and is passed on to young people and future generations, not only evaluated Novruz Bayram as a traditional folk festival, but also valued it as a philosophy of national solidarity and unity. It is no coincidence that the ideas in Heydar Aliyev's speeches during the Novruz holiday celebrations are studied as pages of great importance in our national culture and the history of aesthetic thought.

2.1 The State of Azerbaijan and the National Leader Heydar Aliyev and the national spiritual and aesthetic values. Every stone and pattern of which is history

At this point, it is appropriate to recall the special attention of Heydar Aliyev to the Azerbaijani national spiritual and aesthetic values preserved in the Gobustan rocks, a historical monument of 15,000 years ago, as an area of political management strategy.

The paintings and inscriptions on them undoubtedly tell about the first human fine art in Azerbaijan dating back thousands of years ago, as well as the dialogue culture of the ancient Azerbaijani Turks. The first film about the Gobustan rocks, which is the embodiment of the true philosophical dialogue of the people of the Polyolith era with the world, the universe, as well as the sea and people on the "distant shores", was shot and even filmed twice during the years when the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev, who loved and protected every inch of Azerbaijan and knew deeply the history of ancient modern development, headed the Republic.

This demonstrates the caring attitude of the Great Leader of the Azerbaijani People Heydar Aliyev to the national-spiritual and aesthetic values that live in the soul of our first people in the State Administration Policy, and on the other hand, the high state-people unity of promoting the heritage of our ancestors in the world.

It is no coincidence that the film "Gobustan" shot and released in 1967 by director Ogtay Mirgasimov, scriptwriters Anar Rzayev, Ogtay Mirgasimov, cameraman Zaur Maharramov and composer Faraj Garayev quickly crossed the borders of the country and was met with interest all over the world.

After that, films dedicated to Gobustan, "When the Stones Talk" in 1976 and "Gobustan" in 1997, were shot.

Our carpets, which represent our people's understanding of the world and their outlook on life with colorful shades of aesthetic consciousness, are also famous as the most complete example of our national-spiritual and literary-aesthetic values. The miracle of carpet art, created by our people with loops dyed with the water of plants grown in the rich nature of Azerbaijan, represents the artistic and artistic power of our people. On the other hand, carpets, as valuable examples of our historical culture, introduce us to various peoples and nations in world museums, and serve intercultural dialogue with the impact of colors, the connection of loops, and the content of beauty and solidarity transmitted to millions of eyes and hearts through them.

The great value of ancient Azerbaijani carpets discovered in various historical museums around the world 100 years ago is also one of the successful components of the national state policy of the Great Leader of the Azerbaijani People Heydar Aliyev, the National Strategy of Spiritual and Aesthetic Values in State Administration. Our carpets, which represent our people's understanding of the world and their outlook on life with colorful shades of aesthetic consciousness, are also famous as the most complete example of our national and aesthetic values. Historically, the examples of carpet art created by our people with threads dyed in the water of plants grown in the rich nature of Azerbaijan represent the artistic and artistic power of our people. On the other hand, carpets, as valuable examples of our historical culture, introduce different peoples to us in world museums and serve intercultural dialogue with the content of beauty and solidarity.

Doctor of Art History in Carpet Weaving Roya Tagiyeva expressed the following in her article "Azerbaijani Carpet is Protected as a Universal Value" about Heydar Aliyev's attention and care for our carpet art: "In 1967, the State Museum of Azerbaijan Carpet and Folk Applied Art was organized. However, the museum began its full-scale activity only after the National Leader Heydar Aliyev came to power. As a result of the attention and care shown to folk art by Heydar Aliyev, who always had a native attitude towards our culture and its development, and who was raised and educated in the national spirit, the first exposition of the museum was opened on September 27, 1972. National leader Heydar Aliyev, who personally attended the opening of the museum and gave information about carpets that hold an important place in the life of the Azerbaijani people during his speech and made comparisons, once again emphasized the magnificence of carpet art"¹.

The following quote by art critic Raya Taghiyeva also expresses the fact that Great Leader Heydar Aliyev paid special attention to the strategy of national spiritual and aesthetic values of our people in the policy of state administration: "National Leader Heydar Aliyev closely participated in the opening ceremony of the International Symposium on Azerbaijani Carpets, held with the support of UNESCO in 1983. As a continuation of this tradition, international symposia on Azerbaijani carpets were held in Baku in 1988, 2003, and in Paris in 2007"².

Thus, there is rich material confirming that Great Leader Heydar Aliyev seriously valued National Spiritual and Aesthetic Values in State Administration with official documents. In this context, Great Leader Heydar Aliyev's scientific and objective evaluation of Azerbaijani folk music, mughams, ancient folk epics, and the rich national heritage as a whole is no exception.

3. National classical heritage in the Strategy of National Spiritual and Aesthetic Values

Heydar Aliyev has always kept our folklore, folk art, "Dade Gorgud", Manas", "Koroglu" epics, which are the most complete expression of the ethno-national identity, national spiritual

¹ Tağıyeva Röya. Azərbaycan xalçası ümumbəşəri dəyər kimi qorunur. <http://anl.az/download/meqale/xalqqazeti/2012-/mart/238927.htm>.

² There again

and aesthetic values of the Azerbaijani people, in the center of special attention in his political activities. Heydar Aliyev has always tried to have this ethno-identical, national mentality of ours evaluated at the international level and has achieved this. For example, it is a historical fact that the Great Leader Heydar Aliyev signed a State Decree on holding an international symposium dedicated to the 1300th anniversary of the "Book of Dede Gorgud" epic in Azerbaijan, and Dede Gorgud events were organized in many countries of the world based on this decree. As a result of his own initiative and efforts, the great personality, the powerful National Leader Heydar Aliyev, as the Chairman of the State Commission of this magnificent event held in Baku on November 17, 1999 through UNESCO, constantly attended the meetings of the Symposium Commission, giving his important recommendations. supported the holding of a prestigious event worthy of the name of our people.

Heydar Aliyev also supported the celebration of the 1000th anniversary of the epic "Manas" at the event, saying: "The language of "Manas" is the language of all of us. We are all peoples of the same root, the same language. However, certain differences have emerged in our language over the centuries. By voicing his valuable ideas such as "We hear each other with our hearts, we understand each other with our hearts"¹ - and on a broader geopolitical scale - based on the ideology of Turkism, he highly valued our national and spiritual heritage in the nature of dialogue for the entire world's thought.

The following thoughts of the great leader Heydar Aliyev also express his special importance to human dialogue in these first examples of written literature, national and spiritual values.

"In ancient times, the epics "Dede Gorgud", "Manas", "Alpamash", "Koroglu", our poets and writers belonging to all of our people - Nizami, Yunis Imre, Alisher Navoi, Fuzuli, Nasimi, Madimgulu, Abay and others created immortal works reflecting the history and national values of our people, introducing them to the world, and these have educated our people from generation to generation on the basis of unique national and spiritual values, including universal values, "has prepared, constantly strengthened the feelings of patriotism and loyalty to the homeland"².

Thus, in the article titled "The Concept of National-Spiritual and Aesthetic Values in the Political Heritage of the Great Leader of the Azerbaijani People Heydar Aliyev", in the direction of analyzing the topic, the fact that Great Leader Heydar Aliyev valued a rich human cultural phenomenon at the level of state affairs, from our ethnos to the expression of the mythological consciousness of our people, from our mughams and folk music to our first national operas and operettas, as well as classical European music, also expresses his respect for this national material and spiritual heritage.

Conclusion

Of course, we cannot fully cover the services of the Great Leader of the Azerbaijani people Heydar Aliyev in the field of protection and development of the national spiritual values of his people in one article for 40 years. Because Heydar Aliyev, first as a citizen, dictated by the love of the people and nation, then as a personality Leader elected in his homeland, and later as a head of state promoted to one of the highest positions of his time by his country, did not do as much as he could, but with all his might, with the spirit of our national-spiritual values, our ethnos, mythological monuments belonging to all periods of the history of Azerbaijan, as well as enlightened by the thought monuments of every classical poet, writer, thinker, and created, systematized and developed the Strategy of National-Spiritual and Literary-Aesthetic Values in the management policy of the Independent Azerbaijan state, of which he was the founder.

¹ Heydər Əliyev Müstəqilliyimiz əbədidir.3-cü kitab,Bakı,Azərneşr,1997.Səh.231-232

² Azərbaycan Respublikasının Prezidenti Heydər Əliyevin 1996. Bakıda Türk Yazıçılarının III qurultayında nitqi http://elibrary.bsu.az/yenii/ebookspdf/H.%C6%8Fliyevev_8ci_kitab.pdf.

This strategy, with its educational content and essence, can be applied to the political governance system in advanced and newly emerging countries of the world, as well as to higher, master's, secondary, and even primary education programs.

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